

PROSPECTS FOR THE USING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COGNITIVE THINKING

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Abstract. *This article discusses the increase in the level of emotional sensitivity of students through the use of their pedagogical technologies in the development of cognitive thinking, acceleration of the activity of artistic, logical thinking through the use of pedagogical technologies that encourage students to creative thinking.*

Keywords: *thinking, pedagogical technology, cognitive technology, aesthetic imagination, cognitive learning, emotional intelligence, cognitive therapy, reality, giftedness, literature, folklore, intellectual activity.*

Educational materials with any artistic-aesthetic content, presented in music teaching activities, help students to form aesthetic imaginations. Systematic presentation of knowledge in artistic and aesthetic content according to the age and level of development of students is of particular importance. On the basis of this, students will be able to integrate knowledge and concepts related to music into their experiences, develop artistic thinking, and expand their cognitive abilities. In these educational processes, students will acquire the skills of creative activity with the help of the learning materials they have mastered. For example: they play musical instruments, sing songs, along with performing rhythmic dance movements, they develop the skills of singing according to notes. In this process, students develop cognitive thinking.

It is necessary to develop the cognitive thinking of students in order to expand their imagination regarding material existence. As a result of this approach, there is an opportunity to rapidly develop students' philosophical and logical analytical thinking activities. In this, the verbal educational process is of leading importance. In some cases, not enough attention is paid to the development of visual-motor and figurative thinking of students. In this process, intuition is approached as a symbol of practical activity. In order to expand the possibilities of students' cognitive acceptance of educational materials, it is necessary to teach them to feel things and events in the environment, artistic and aesthetic tools [4].

Aesthetic knowledge becomes a worldview with the help of social perspective and scientific knowledge of the intellect in pedagogical views on the development of personal thinking. Today, attention is paid to this issue at the level of state policy. The idea of developing the cultural and spiritual thinking of students, and the wide use of the possibilities of art in forming their aesthetic outlook and taste is being promoted. In particular, the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan[1], the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2020 No. Decree 6000 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society"[2].

Specific knowledge presented in educational materials reflecting musical content will become practical experiences of students. In these processes, teachers should systematically organize pedagogical situations that are convenient for the analysis, generalization, and cognitive

acceptance of the presented artistic-aesthetic knowledge. As a result, the presented knowledge and concepts are analyzed by students and their content is understood.

As a result of the use of pedagogical technologies, the educational process acquires its own characteristics. For this purpose, it becomes possible to ensure the effectiveness of education as a result of analyzing the processes of using pedagogical technologies and determining effective methods. In the process of music education, the knowledge of artistic and aesthetic content presented for each subject is selected and structured.

Only when the educational materials presented to students have an artistic and aesthetic content will they affect their subconscious, enrich their thinking, aesthetic worldview, emotional world, and expand the possibility of receiving certain knowledge. The use of cognitive technologies in the formation of students' thinking with the help of educational materials of artistic and aesthetic content in cognitive educational processes creates pedagogical situations that allow to achieve the expected efficiency in training sessions.

Cognitive education - 1. education to expand the range of knowledge about the environment, to form differentiating thinking, to develop cognitive needs. 2. one of the fields of psychological research and directions of pedagogy. K.t. as the main goal of development of intellectual abilities of the individual. Teaching based on a set of educational strategies aimed at increasing the student's ability to adapt to the acquisition of new knowledge is interpreted as [3; p. 180].

As a result of cognitive acceptance of educational materials with musical content, cognitive thinking develops in students.

Cognitive acceptance of educational materials means that students creatively assimilate the knowledge presented to them and turn it into skills.[5]

Emotional intelligence is the basis of cognitive thinking. This is reflected in students' ability to understand and manage their emotions. These skills help students to find solutions to tasks and solve life problems. The level of cognitive intelligence depends on the cognitive skills and individual characteristics of students. A student with developed cognitive thinking performs the following actions:

- ability to perform creative activities;
- understanding reality;
- remembering information of artistic and aesthetic content;
- focus on one point;
- ability to coordinate ideas;
- have a broad vision;
- making appropriate decisions;
- logical thinking;

Through the use of cognitive technologies and their application in the process of music education, the concepts of creative cognition are formed in students, together with the increase of their interest in educational materials of artistic and aesthetic content, the concept of musical thinking develops in them.

Students acquire certain skills only when they are able to develop their cognitive thinking. Teachers should base their practice on cognitive behavioral therapy. This method is effective in developing students' cognitive ability. These methods have shown that the quality of students' educational activities and the level of their cognitive abilities directly depend on their thinking and

perception, and its development with the help of educational materials of artistic and aesthetic content is of great pedagogical value. There are many methods and ways to develop students' cognitive abilities with the help of educational materials of artistic and aesthetic content. These are:

- Organization of "Socratic question-and-answer" situations with the help of the provided educational materials by ensuring that educational materials with artistic and aesthetic content encourage students to think creatively, making effective use of the text of classic songs and chants, sayings;

- Organizing social events. In this case, conducting musical competitions based on the text of the songs in the alphabet style;

- In the process of implementing this cognitive technology, the method of working in groups or pairs is used;

- performing musical-rhythmic movements, ensuring harmony of movements with music;

- playing folk games expressed in folklore music samples. In this process, the interpretation of the meanings expressed in the music is carried out.

Organization of the game "Remembering the names of musical tones". In this, one of the students plays the tune and the others find its name. Students who remember the most names of music and provide historical information about it are the winners. In the framework of this didactic game, students can collect narratives, historical events, and photos about certain music. Such games have the ability to strengthen students' memory, stabilize their interests, create motivation for learning and collecting new information, and develop reflexive skills. In addition, in order to develop the cognitive abilities of students, it is possible to organize logical question-and-answer games, musical riddles, and work situations on crosswords.

By using these pedagogical technologies, it is possible to organize logical question-and-answer games, musical riddles, and work on crossword puzzles in order to develop students' cognitive thinking.

Such musical puzzles help the students to retain national music examples, composers, and the names of the works they created in a deeper memory, as well as to form ideas about musical terms.

In music lessons, "Intellectual games" also allow to achieve efficiency and, together with the development of students' cognitive thinking, expand their opportunities for creative assimilation of educational materials. Instead, intellectual games have a complex character and encourage students to think deeply, think, and use all their knowledge. Such games ensure mental activity of students and encourage more creativity and initiative. These pedagogical technologies are as follows.

- "Night and day" (Minor-major). This didactic game also expands students' opportunities to strengthen their musical memory, gain knowledge about the work of composers and composers, and understand the essence of the musical works created by them. In addition, such didactic games have a positive effect on the emotional world of students.

- "Audio music training". In this, an unfamiliar piece of music is presented to the students, and in order to develop the listening comprehension skills of the students, the following questions are put before them:

- determine the character of the music, imagine the images expressed in it,

- what idea is presented in this work, and in the second situation, video materials related to the music work are presented and questions are asked about which work it is and its author. Such didactic situations make it possible to determine students' musical knowledge, listening comprehension skills, and musical memories.

- "Musical image" exercise. In the next lesson, students are presented with several pictures and asked to choose musical tones that will help reveal their meaning. In this process, students' aesthetic taste, ability to cognitively perceive the balance between artistic image and music is developed.

- Organizing a "musical trip". In this process, a number of composers and composers (S.Yudakov, M.Leviev, Domla Halim Ibodov, Haji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, K.Otaniyozov, O.Khudayshukurov, M.Uzokov, Mukarrama Turgunboeva, Yu.Rajabi) were introduced to the students. It is possible to take a trip to the home museums of Uzbek music artists, to the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan. Such travel lessons help students to develop their imagination and cultural outlook on Uzbek national music art and culture.

Working with these methods not only makes the teacher comfortable, but also effectively forms the cognitive abilities of students.

With the help of cognitive technologies, students acquire the following skills:

- to have extraordinary talent;
- formation of the ability to receive large amounts of information;
- can easily receive and analyze information;
- making reliable conclusions and making firm decisions;
- ability to approach tasks not only logically, but creatively;

Another important method is the method of cognitive analysis of each student's level of mastery of the knowledge presented in the educational materials of artistic and aesthetic content. As a result of the analysis of the student's creative abilities and actions, it implies the identification of cognitive factors that affect the personality of the student. As a result, it is necessary to determine the cognitive methods that have a greater impact on students, to determine the extent of knowledge and experience they have, to realize the hidden creative potential of students with the help of cognitive methods. Analytical results are obtained using these methods.

The teacher should create a favorable pedagogical situation to creatively influence students in educational activities. Cognitive methods are important in identifying students' hidden talents.

In summary, as a result of the regular use of cognitive technologies and methods in musical pedagogical processes, students have a certain level of artistic-aesthetic taste, musical thinking, creative skills, creative and intellectual activities, reflection of educational materials, and aesthetic evaluation skills. develops.

REFERENCES

1. 2018 йил 28 ноябрдаги ПҚ–4038-сон «Ўзбекистон Республикасида миллий маданиятни янада ривожлантириш концепцияси тўғрисида»ги Қарори.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 26 майдаги ПФ-6000-сон “Маданият ва санъат соҳасининг жамият ҳаётидаги ўрни ва таъсирини янада ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги фармони
3. Педагогика: энциклопедия. II жилд / тузувчилар: жамоа.//Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” Давлат илмий нашриёти. 2015. – 376 б.

4. Safarova R.G. Iqtidorli o'quvchilarda kreativ fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodlari va vositalari. "Ta'limda kognitiv jarayonlarni faollashtirishning ilmiy-metodik talqini (PBL – 5 yondashuvi: muammoga, loyihaga, ishlab chiqarishga, jarayonga va shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish)" mavzusidagi an'anaviy ko'p tarmoqli xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. 2023-yil 16–17-iyun.
5. Shomurodov J.O. O'quvchilarning badiiy-estetik mazmundagi o'quv materiallarini kognitiv qabul qilish layoqatini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari ped. fan. falsafa dok. (PhD) diss. - T.: 2023. - 156 b.